

Isomers of Fullerenes C_{58} to C_{60}

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(Received 12 October, 2023)

We have designed possible structures of isomers of fullerenes from C_{58} to C_{60} . The fullerenes studied refer to four-, five- and six-fold symmetry, they being divided into two classes, perfect (basic) having ordinary symmetry and intermediate having topological symmetry. We have used three the most natural mechanisms of their formation, namely, fusion of carbon cupolas having the same symmetry; fusion of fullerenes having compatible symmetry and embedding carbon dimers into the hexagons with a specific surrounding of initial fullerenes. The energies of the fullerenes calculated through the use of molecular mechanics are presented together with their graphs. We have separated fragments of curvature and put into accordance with their centers the centers of principal stresses. The arrangement of both centers for the five observed experimentally isomers of fullerene C_{60} corresponds to five geometric figures: icosahedron, pentagonal, hexagonal, deformed hexagonal bipyramids and cube. As a result the binding energy of isomers can be considered not only as a global quantity, but as a surface distribution.

PACS numbers: 11.10.-z, 11.15.Ha, 12.38.Bx

Keywords: atomic isomer, dimer embedding, energy, fullerene, fusion reaction, graph representation, growth, periodic system, symmetry

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12621762>

1. Introduction

The fullerene C_{60} is the most abundant and the most celebrated carbon spheroid but its structure up to now is the subject for

discussion [1]. During our numerous investigations on fullerenes [1, 2] we have come to conclusion that in order to clarify the problem of fullerene C_{60} isomers, it is necessary to change the style of study. Instead of the trying of solving the task for fullerene C_{60} , it is more reasonable to begin with simplest fullerenes. With this in mind, we have studied the structure and energy of fullerene

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isomers in the range from C_4 to C_{58} [3-7].

In doing so, we have obtained perfect fullerenes C_{14} , C_{20} , C_{26} , C_{32} , C_{38} and C_{44} having three-fold symmetry (D_{3h}). Then we found perfect fullerenes C_{16} , C_{24} , C_{32} , C_{38} , C_{40} , C_{48} , C_{56} and C_{64} of four-fold symmetry (D_{4h}) [8, 9]. The mass difference between successive fullerenes in the first case is $\Delta m = 6$, in the second case $\Delta m = 8$. It should be emphasized that in both cases the mass difference is equal to a double degree of symmetry. We supposed that this empirical rule is valid for fullerenes of other symmetries. In this case one should obtain during the growth of fullerenes originating from fullerene C_{20} (D_{5h} symmetry) perfect fullerenes C_{30} , C_{40} , C_{50} , C_{60} , C_{70} and C_{80} , the fullerenes conserving five-fold symmetry with $\Delta m = 10$. In a similar way, during the growth of fullerenes originating from fullerene C_{24} (D_{6h} symmetry) perfect fullerenes C_{36} , C_{48} , C_{60} , C_{72} , C_{84} and C_{96} conserving six-fold symmetry must be formed with $\Delta m = 12$. Succeeding studies confirmed these predictions [10, 11].

According to Georg Wilhelm Friedrich Hegel (1770-1831), synthesis ($\sigma\nu\nu\theta\varepsilon\sigma\iota\zeta$ is joining) is the highest grade of development, which resolves the contradictions of previous stages. It is intriguing to combine periodicities, Δm and Δn , in order to gain a better understanding of the results obtained. In doing so, we have created for the first time in 2017 the periodic table [11, 12] where all the fullerenes form five vertical columns (groups), having different symmetry.

The periodic system of fullerenes predicts their symmetry as well as the existence of their isomers of different symmetry [2]. In this contribution we present the classification of fullerene isomers, give their structure and energy for two fullerenes, C_{58} and mainly C_{60} . We will give the structure of the fullerenes for two extreme electronic configurations: with single bonds only

and with single and double ones, the maximum number of possible double bonds being positioned symmetrically. Much attention is given also to the ways of obtaining the isomers of fullerene C_{60} .

FIG. 1. (Color online) Fullerene C_{58} as a result of embedding a carbon dimer into fullerene C_{56} : structure and graphs; energy E in kJ/mol.

FIG. 2. (Color online) Fullerene C_{58} as a result of embedding four carbon dimers into fullerene C_{50} : structure and graphs; energy E in kJ/mol.

2. Basic perfect and intermediate imperfect fullerenes

According to the periodic system of fullerenes, there are two main types of fullerenes; the basic perfect ones and intermediate imperfect ones. The basic perfect fullerenes have ideal structure and common symmetry. The intermediate imperfect fullerenes have extra carbon dimers. We have defined the imperfect fullerenes, which conserve the main

FIG. 3. (Color online) Fullerene C_{58} of six-fold symmetry: structure and graphs; energy E in kJ/mol.

axis of common symmetry, as having topological symmetry.

3. Isomers of fullerene C_{58}

We have systemized possible ways of forming the isomers of fullerenes [4]. It turned out that there are three the most natural mechanisms of their growth.

1) Endo-Kroto: embedding carbon dimers into the hexagons of initial fullerenes;

2) Melker–Vorobyeva: fusion of the carbon cupolas having the same symmetry;

3) Melker–Krupina: fusion of fullerenes having compatible symmetry.

The first mechanism creates both perfect and imperfect fullerenes; the second and third do only perfect.

The periodic system of fullerenes predicts that there could be three imperfect isomers C_{58} of topological symmetry which have four-, five- and six-fold symmetry [11].

3.1. Fullerene C_{58} of four-fold symmetry

The ancestor fullerene C_{56} belongs to the column of basic perfect fullerenes having four-fold symmetry. It can produce the natural isomer shown in Fig. 1. There is one point to be made. Any fullerene, which nearest ancestor is a perfect fullerene, has no isomers of the same topological symmetry.

3.2. Fullerene C_{58} of five-fold symmetry

For fullerene C_{58} , the nearest perfect ancestor neighbor fullerene is C_{50} . The atomic structure corresponding to a perfect polyhedron consists of two isolated pentagons, five sets of adjacent pentagons and fifteen hexagons, so it is a *penta*₁₂-*hexa*₁₅ polyhedron. One can design fullerene C_{58} by embedding four carbon dimers into this perfect fullerene. The fullerene obtained is presented in Fig. 2. Here one has a similar situation as before. Any fullerene, which nearest succedent is a perfect fullerene, has no isomers of the same topological symmetry.

3.3. Fullerene C_{58} of six-fold symmetry

For fullerene C_{58} , the nearest-neighbor perfect fullerene is C_{48} , which has two isomers [6]. One is a dead fullerene, the other can grow and produce fullerene C_{58} . The fullerenes are presented in Fig. 3.

4. Isomers of fullerene C_{60}

The most abundant and most celebrated fullerene is molecule C_{60} , so we consider it in detail. The periodic system of fullerenes predicts that there could be one isomer C_{60} of four-fold topological symmetry and two isomers of five- and six-fold common symmetry [11].

4.1. Fullerene C_{60} of four-fold symmetry

The ancestor, perfect fullerene C_{56} belongs to the column of fullerenes having four-fold symmetry (Fig. 1). It can produce two isomers of topological four-fold symmetry, asymmetric and symmetric; they are shown in Fig. 4.

The symmetric fullerene is semi-perfect and has not only topological four-fold symmetry but also two-fold ordinary symmetry. From mathematical point of view it refers to a subgroup of the corresponding group. According to the Lagrange's theorem, the order of a subgroup is a divisor of a group [13]. This takes place here.

4.2. Fullerene C_{60} of five-fold symmetry

4.2.1. Dimer embedding

For fullerene C_{60} , the nearest perfect ancestor neighbor fullerene is C_{50} . One can design fullerene C_{60} by embedding five carbon dimers into this perfect fullerene [10]. The fullerene

FIG. 4. (Color online) Fullerene C_{60} as a result of embedding two carbon dimers into fullerene C_{56} : structure and graphs; energy E in kJ/mol.

obtained is presented in Fig. 5.

The growth of fullerene C_{50} can come in another way producing non-classical fullerenes [10]. As a result, one obtains fullerene C_{60} with only pentagons and heptagons (Fig. 6). It is also a perfect fullerene.

FIG. 5. (Color online) Fullerene C_{60} as a result of embedding five carbon dimers into fullerene C_{50} normal to the five-fold axis: structure and graphs; energy E in kJ/mol.

FIG. 6. (Color online) Fullerene C_{60} as a result of embedding five carbon dimers into fullerene C_{50} parallel to the five-fold axis: structure and graphs; energy E in kJ/mol.

As noted above, there is the second mechanism of fullerene's growth, fusion of the carbon cupolas having the same symmetry. The fullerene C_{60} obtained by the second mechanism through the fusion of two cupolas C_{30} was obtained in [10] and is presented in Fig. 7.

FIG. 7. (Color online) Result of joining two cupolas C_{30} of five-fold symmetry: the rotation-reflection symmetry fusion, structure and graphs; energy E in kJ/mol.

Its atomic structure corresponding to a perfect polyhedron is a truncated icosahedron, which consists of twelve isolated pentagons and twenty adjacent hexagons. It is the most abundant and most celebrated fullerene molecule.

4.3. Corannulene path of producing fullerene C_{60}

Above we have designed the most abundant and most celebrated fullerene molecule C_{60} by fusion of two cupolas C_{30} . It should be emphasized that the formation and structure of

cupolas was postulated. The question arises: Are there in nature similar molecules, from which it is possible to obtain the cupolas? Consider the analogy with house-building. It is clear that more cheaply and easier to build a house from blocks than from bricks. In the case of fullerenes, the nature gives us the ready blocks in the form of corannulene $C_{20}H_{10}$ of C_{5v} symmetry. This molecule is usually considered as a key fullerene fragment [14, 15]. Being π -conjugated compound, it has a cupola-shaped species which is presented in Fig. 8. Replacing hydrogen atoms with carbon ones, we obtain cement for binding together the blocks.

Corannulene $C_{20}H_{10}$ $E=245$

FIG. 8. (Color online) Corannulene as a cupola; energy E in kJ/mol.

Suppose that we have removed ten hydrogen atoms from corannulene, then we obtain cupola C_{20} . If afterwards to add ten carbon atoms to the cupola, one gets cupola C_{30} . (Fig. 9) Fusion of two cupolas leads to appearance of the most famous fullerene molecule C_{60} (Fig. 7). To gain a better understanding of the fusion reactions, their main

features are given in the form of scheme (Fig. 10).

FIG. 9. (Color online) Carbon cupolas generated on the basis of corannulene: energy in E kJ/mol.

These results deserve further comment. The mechanism of fusion resembles that of known in biophysics as lock-key adhesion [16]. The adhesion is due to the formation of specific molecular bonds between complementary pairs of proteins which are denoted by “lock” (L) and “key” (K). In our case the boundary-atom configurations of cupolas play simultaneously the role both lock and key.

For the corannulene cupolas the LK atoms are rather rigidly connected with the whole cupolas by two interatomic bonds; it follows from Fig. 10a.

FIG. 10. (Color online) Scheme reflecting the main structural changes during the fusion of cupolas: a) boundary-atom configuration of separate cupolas; b) fusion zone.

4.4. Sumanene path of creating fullerene

C_{60}

4.4.1. Structure of fullerene obtained

Similar to corannulene $C_{20}H_{10}$ of $C_{5\nu}$ symmetry, sumanene $C_{21}H_{12}$, which possesses $C_{3\nu}$ symmetry, is also considered as a key fullerene fragment [14, 15]. Being also π -conjugated compound, it has a cupola-shaped species (Fig. 11). However the mechanism of fullerene assembly from such fragments is not known. By analogy with corannulene it is possible to obtain from sumanene successively cupolas C_{21} and C_{30} and afterwards fullerene C_{60} (Figs. 12 and 13). Interestingly enough that the final structures of the fullerenes obtained by different ways are the same. However, in the second case there are possible fusion-faults (Fig. 14).

FIG. 11. (Color online) Sumanene as a bowl; energy E in kJ/mol.

FIG. 12. (Color online) Carbon cupolas generated on the basis of sumanene: energy E in kJ/mol.

FIG. 13. (Color online) Fullerene C_{60} obtained by the fusion of two “sumanene” cupolas C_{30} : energy E in kJ/mol.

4.4.2. Defects of fusion

Structure of fullerenes obtained. Consider the fusion reactions in detail. As a result of the reactions, at first the distorted polyhedrons are fashioned (Fig. 14). It should be emphasized that there are possible four types of the reaction, namely: perfect reaction (Fig. 14a); one-fault reaction (Fig. 14b); two-fault reaction (Fig. 14c); and three-fault reaction (Fig. 14d).

The structures shown above relax into a perfect polyhedron (Fig. 15a) or faulted structure polyhedrons (Fig. 15b, c, and d). The perfect reaction leads to creation of 20 isolated pentagons (Fig. 15a). The faulted reactions differ in the number of pentagon pairs formed, namely, two (Fig. 15b), three (Fig. 15c) and four (Fig. 15d).

The perfect fullerene C_{60} can be imagined as the octahedral arrangement of the pyracylene units. A pyracylene unit contains two pentagons and two hexagons and a central reactive double bond [10]. One of the units is shaded in Fig. 15a; the atoms of the central bond are marked in orange. The faulted fullerene, presented in Fig. 15b, looks, as if its shaded pyracylene unit had undergone the Stone-Wales transformation [17-19]. Its boundary atoms are the same; they are connected by red lines. The transformation

FIG. 14. (Color online) Fusion of two “sumanene” cupolas C_{30} : a) perfect reaction, b) one-fault reaction, c) two-fault reaction, d) three-fault reaction.

corresponds to the rotation of the central bond by 90 degrees, resulting in the creation of two adjacent pentagon-pentagon pairs; their atoms connected by the bonds marked in red too (Fig. 15b'). In a similar way one can think over other faulted fullerenes.

Contrary to corannulene, for the “sumanene” cupolas thermal fluctuations are more important for the LK atoms, since each atom is connected with the cupolas only by one bond (Fig. 16a). As a result, the “sumanene” fullerenes contain fusion faults (Fig. 16b).

FIG. 15. (Color online) “Sumanene” fullerene C_{60} : energy E in kJ/mol.

4.4.3. Annealing of defects

Five isomers of fullerene C_{60} were generated in microwave plasma of chloroform [20]. They were stable at room temperature but four of them disintegrated at 250°C . The authors have suggested possible structures and calculated the formation energies of these isomers. However, a thinkable pattern of final configuration does not guarantee that the postulated configurations coincide with the structures obtained experimentally. It seems more reasonable to study the defect configurations obtained by one of well-known mechanism of fullerene formation, which demonstrated its

validity in many cases. This raises the question how to choose the best mechanism. To our mind, the best mechanism must satisfy the principle of least action. As a rule, this principle is tightly connected with symmetry and conservation laws.

We have chosen the cupola-fusion mechanism and in the case of “sumanene” path of fullerene creation have obtained three defect-isomers of fullerene C_{60} . The question arises of the paths of their evolution into an equilibrium configuration of buckminsterfullerene. In other words, what is the mechanism of defect annealing that reduces the energy of the cluster. Defect annealing occurs by local rearrangement carbon bonds and is the reverse process of

FIG. 16. (Color online) Scheme reflecting the main structural changes during the fusion of cupolas: a) boundary-atom configuration of separate cupolas; a') fusion zone, perfect reaction; b) fusion zone, one-fault reaction.

defect formation. Mention was made that the fullerenes having fusion defects look, as if their pyracylene unit had undergone the Stone-Wales transformation. From this statement logical deduction can be drawn that the annealing mechanism is the reverse Stone-Wales transformation shown in Fig. 17.

FIG. 17. (Color online) Scheme of the reverse Stone-Wales transformation.

FIG. 18. (Color online) Joining of a graphene fragment C_{24} and a cupola C_{36} : a) separate carbon cupola and graphene fragment; b) intermediate compound; c) final polyhedron.

FIG. 19. (Color online) Structure, energy and graphs of fullerene C_{60} with single and double bonds; energy E in kJ/mol.

4.4.4. Cupola fusion then dimer embedding

Fusion of the carbon cupolas having the same symmetry was first used in [22]. The authors suggested that fullerene can grow by reacting with each other, similar to a bubble growth in a soap solution. As the fullerenes they considered truncated pyramids. Later the term “pyramid” was substituted for another term “cupola”. In doing so they obtained fullerene C_{48} having six-

FIG. 20. (Color online) Fusion of two cupolas C_{24} : a) separate carbon cupolas; b) intermediate compound; c) final polyhedron.

FIG. 21. (Color online) Fullerene C_{48} as a result of joining two cupolas C_{24} of six-fold symmetry: the mirror symmetry fusion, structure and graphs; energy E in kJ/mol.

fold symmetry. It is shown in Figs. 20 and 21.

4.5. Fullerene C_{60} of six-fold symmetry

4.5.1. Fusion cupola

One can design this fullerene of six-fold symmetry by means of the second mechanism through the fusion of a graphene fragment C_{24} and a cupola C_{36} [21] as shown in Fig. 18. The fullerene obtained contains six pairs of two

adjacent pentagons and twenty hexagons. It is a $penta_{12}-hexa_{15}$ polyhedron of six-fold symmetry (Fig. 19).

Starting with this fullerene, one can obtain the direct descendents through the use of End-Kroto mechanism (dimer embedding into hexagons [23]). It was done in Ref. [11] where the fullerenes from C_{48} to C_{60} were designed. The scheme of growth is illustrated in Fig. 22; its main features are presented in Fig. 23. It is interesting to note that the obtained structure is identical to that shown in Fig. 19, although the latter was designed through the fusion of a graphene fragment C_{24} and a cupola C_{36} .

There are a number of points to be made. In Ref. [11] it was shown that fullerene C_{48} can grow in various manners: from one center (e.g. Fig. 23) or from two centers (e.g. Fig. 22). As a result one obtains intermediate isomers having different symmetries. For example, fullerene C_{56} of Fig. 22 has D_{2h} symmetry whereas fullerene C_{56} of Fig. 23 does D_{1h} . The following fullerene C_{58} has D_{1h} symmetry in both cases, but the final fullerene C_{60} gets D_{6h} symmetry. It should be emphasized that in both cases dimer embedding is realized normal to the six-fold symmetry axis.

However, fullerene C_{56} of Fig. 22 can grow in another way as shown in Fig. 24. Here is dimer embedding is made at an angle to the axis of symmetry. As a result we have the isomer of fullerene C_{60} containing two chains of six pentagons (Fig. 25). To gain a better understanding of the mechanism of dimer embedding, its main features are presented in Fig. 26.

4.5.2. Fullerene fusion then dimer embedding

Fusion of the carbon fullerenes having compatible symmetry was first considered in [24]. The authors carefully investigated the physical

FIG. 22. (Color online) Scheme of the growth of fullerene C_{48} having six-fold symmetry.

restrictions which are imposed on mathematical models used for designing the process. Later they obtained fullerene C_{48} having six-fold symmetry through the use of this mechanism. Its shape resembles a truncated ovaloid and is shown in Fig. 27.

The structure of fullerene C_{48} is also rather interesting. The fullerene contains two clusters of eighteen atoms, each cluster having six pentagons forming a ring around a hexagon in the center. The clusters are separated by a zigzag ring of twelve atoms. From the figure it follows that the fullerene has six-fold rotation-reflection symmetry D_{6d} .

The subsequent growth is shown in Figs. 28 and 29.

4.5.3. Successor of four-fold symmetry: dimer embedding

Up to now we have considered so called “linear growth” of fullerenes when the growing object conserves symmetry, ordinary or topological. It resembles the growth of coniferous trees. Contrary to them deciduous trees grow frequently in such manner that one of side branches begin to prevail over the main one.

Such situation is also possible for fullerenes. In doing so, a fullerene is changing its symmetry. For example, fullerene C_{44} of the four-fold symmetry can grow in such a way as shown in Fig. 30. Here the dimer embedding is made at the Frigid Zone near the axis of symmetry. As a result we have the isomer of fullerene C_{60} containing four isolated pentagons and four conjugate pentagons (Fig. 31). To gain a better understanding of the structure obtained, the

FIG. 23. (Color online) Main structural changes during the growth of fullerene C_{48} .

FIG. 24. (Color online) Scheme of the growth of fullerene C_{56} having two-fold symmetry.

FIG. 25. (Color online) Structure, energy and graphs of fullerene C_{60} with single and double bonds; energy E in kJ/mol.

FIG. 26. (Color online) Main structural changes during the growth of fullerene C_{56} .

space arrangement of conjugated pentagons is presented schematically in Fig. 32.

5. Fullerene energy: it depends on what?

5.1. Energy of isomers

In Fig. 33 there are given the structure, graphs and energy of the isomers of fullerene

FIG. 27. (Color online) Joining two fullerenes C_{24} ; structure and graphs; energy E in kJ/mol.

C_{60} . How to understand these data? It seems reasonable to turn to Aristotle for advice. Aristotle (A $\rho\iota\sigma\tau\omicron\tau\epsilon\lambda\eta\varsigma$, 384-322, B.C.) had written the book “ $\Phi\upsilon\sigma\iota\kappa\alpha$ ” (Nature) [1]. “In the science on nature first of all it is necessary to define what refers to the elements, reasons or notions of physics. After all, we are sure in the knowledge of any thing, when we know its first reasons, first elements. The natural path to that is from the less evident by nature, but more evident for us, to the more evident and known by nature. Not a goal is an object of study, but the means of goal achievement.”

5.2. Fragments of curvature

5.2.1. Fragments of curvature

In Ref. [25] we have carefully discussed the interrelation between the fullerene surface, its curvature and distortion energy. In mathematics the curvature is defined as the quantity which characterizes a deviation of a surface from a plane at a given point [26]. The deviation of a surface from a plane is studied in the following manner. Through the normal at a given point of surface all the possible planes are drawn. The sections of surface by these planes are called

normal sections, the curvatures of normal sections being normal curvatures of the surface at a given point. Maximum and minimum curvatures are called principal curvatures. Their combinations give Gauss and average curvatures which are used for analysis of the surface curvature.

We will follow to Aristotle trying finding the elements of fullerenes, which define its surface curvature. In other words, we will search first of all “fragment of curvature”, but not the curvature value. Analysis of the structures shown in Fig. 33 allows us to separate the following fragments of curvature (Fig. 34).

There are two types of curvature fragments. One has a curvature center in the middle of a pentagon (CF-5) another in the center of a double bond connecting two adjacent pentagons (CF-8). It should be emphasized that an isolated center CF-6 does not creates curvature; it becomes a curvature center under the influence of surroundings. Besides, there are complex fragments of curvature, chain and cupola, having several centers (Fig. 35).

5.2.2. Geometry of curvature’s centers

From Figs. 34 and 35 follows that the fragments of curvature have certain symmetry. We name the centers of fragments as curvature centers. The study of their arrangement in different isomers has given the following picture (Fig. 36). Thus we have the structure of all the experimentally observed isomers of fullerene C_{60} [26]. The first isomer is perfect, the other are imperfect and differ in the number of pairs of two adjacent pentagons. It should be emphasized that the imperfect isomers possess topological symmetry.

It is known that the less is the fullerene surface, the less its distortion energy [1, 25]. The least energy has the icosahedron of 12 curvature

FIG. 28. (Color online) Scheme of the growth of fullerene C_{48} obtained by fusion of two fullerenes C_{24} having six-fold symmetry.

FIG. 29. (Color online) Structure and graphs of fullerene C_{60} with single and double bonds; energy E in kJ/mol.

centers. In its turn, the local curvature is defined by the sum of adjacent angles having a common vertex. The larger is the sum, the less is curvature, and therefore the less is local stress concentration. The largest sum has the fullerene in the form of a truncated icosahedron with isolated pentagons, $2 \cdot 120 + 108 = 348$, all other configurations contain adjacent pentagons and here the largest sum is equal to $2 \cdot 108 + 120 = 336$. As a result, they have a larger energy.

FIG. 30. (Color online) Scheme of the growth of fullerene C_{44} having topological four-fold symmetry.

6. Isomers: geometry in chemistry

“For the correct judgment on the state of any science to-day and its perspectives, it is always useful to look back at its past, sometimes even at very remoteness” (S. I. Vavilov) [27]. What

one can see in the past? In September 1861 Professor of Kazan University (Russia) A. M. Butlerov had given a report at the 36th meeting of German naturalists and physicians in Spyer. The report bore the name “Something on the chemical structure of substances” [30]. Butlerov affirmed

FIG. 31. (Color online) Structure and graphs of fullerene C_{60} with single and double bonds originated from fullerene C_{44} of the four-fold symmetry; energy E in kJ/mol.

FIG. 32. (Color online) Arrangement of the conjugated pentagons of fullerene C_{60} originated from fullerene C_{44} of the four-fold symmetry.

“Each chemical atom, entering into a substance, acts with definite forces upon surrounding atoms. As a result, the atoms are tied up into a chemical particle, a molecule in a definite order, which I name ‘chemical structure’. From this it follows that chemical nature of complex particles is defined by the nature of their constituents, their number and their structure”.

Later Butlerov added that “The main that I declare in my new theory is that atoms occupy definite positions. In dependence of that they show different properties. Taking into account the order of atomic position in a molecule, one must expect the existence of several isomers for many substances”.

In 1863 there have been discovered four isomers of butyl alcohols. Butlerov made

an important conclusion that “If having the same composition, the substances have different properties; they must have different chemical structure”. Later isomers of more complex compounds were discovered and Butlerov decided to apply his structural theory to all the known reactions and compounds of organic chemistry and with this purpose to write a new text-book on organic chemistry. It took many years. In 1866, “Lehrbuch der organischen Chemie” was done [30].

7. Discussion and conclusion

We use the notions, curvature as continuity and the centers of curvature as discontinuity. It should be emphasized that in mathematics there are such notion as curvature, tensor of

FIG. 33. (Color online) Structure and graphs of the isomers of fullerene C_{60} ; energy E in kJ/mol.

FIG. 34. (Color online) Curvature fragments of the isomers of fullerene C_{60} .

FIG. 35. (Color online) Complex curvature fragments of the isomers of fullerene C_{60} .

curvature [26], but no words about tensor of stress [28]. In mechanics and physics they say about stress, field curvature, but consider these notions separately [29]. We assume that the curvature centers are connected with the centers of stress concentration. To our mind they are identical. Therefore, first of all it is necessary

FIG. 36. (Color online) Curvature polyhedrons of the isomers of fullerene C_{60} ; energy E in kJ/mol.

to find the curvature centers. In doing so, we gain the arrangement of stress concentration, can apply the elasticity theory not only to the fullerenes (this task is very cumbersome) but to the polyhedrons of curvature centers (this task is easier). Since the curvature polyhedrons resemble crystals, and the crystals are studied many years [29], we can use their knowledge for understanding such processes as, e.g. sublimation, fracture of fullerenes. Moreover, even the binding energy of fullerenes can be considered not only as a global quantity, but as a surface distribution. As a result, we can gain more profound insight into their nature.

We have studied structures and energies of fullerenes, C_{58} and C_{60} . According to the periodic table of fullerenes these objects have four-, five-, and six-fold symmetry and produce the manifold of isomers. The latter can be divided into two classes, perfect basic fullerenes and imperfect intermediate ones. The basic perfect fullerenes have ideal structure and common symmetry. The intermediate imperfect fullerenes have adjacent pentagons bounded by dimers. By analogy with crystal physics, we can assume that these extra dimers play the role of defects which violate the common symmetry and create local

imperfections. However, for defect crystals the long-range-order is observed experimentally. In order to underline this peculiarity, such long-range order is referred to as the topological long-range one. Using analogous terminology, we have defined the imperfect fullerenes, which conserve the main axis of common symmetry, as having topological symmetry.

We have used three the most natural mechanisms of their formation, namely, fusion of carbon cupolas having the same symmetry; fusion of fullerenes having compatible symmetry and embedding carbon dimers into the hexagons with a specific surrounding of initial fullerenes. The energies of the fullerenes calculated through the use of molecular mechanics are presented together with their graphs.

We have separated fragments of curvature and put into accordance with their centers the centers of principal stresses. The arrangement of both centers for the five isomers of fullerene C_{60} observed experimentally corresponds to five geometric figures: icosahedron, pentagonal, hexagonal, deformed hexagonal bipyramids and cube. As a result the binding energy of isomers can be considered not only as a global quantity, but as a surface distribution.

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